

Review

PROMOTION OF SWEET SORGHUM CULTIVATION FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE AND ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION IN SOUTHERN NIGERIA

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Received:

21 July 2023

Accepted for publication

14 September 2023

Published

20 October 2023

KEYWORDS

Sweet sorghum,
Crop diversification, Climate change, Food security.

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Abstract

The negative impact of Nigeria's dependence on fossil fuel as its major source of energy and foreign exchange, and the fact that over 90% of the nation's ethanol requirement is imported have brought about the need to look for alternative sources of ethanol, particularly from crops. Ethanol has become a 'renewable liquid gold' with the recent outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic as it is a major raw material in the production of sanitizers. Local ethanol production from crops offers a sustainable eco-friendly energy option and will make a direct and sustainable impact on gainful youth employment, food security, and improved livelihoods for the populace. In this vein, only ethanol produced from sweet sorghum (unlike cassava and maize) does not compromise food security as farmers can use its grains for food or feed and stalks for ethanol production. Northern Nigeria accounted for almost 99% of the nation's total sorghum production. However, the region is affected by climate change and desert encroachment, thereby resulting in a decline in national sorghum output. Though recent research has shown that Southern Nigeria is very suitable for the cultivation of sorghum, there is a need to evaluate factors that can promote the adoption of sweet sorghum. Practices to improve the resilience of systems and populations to climate change and other stresses include economic diversification through the promotion of climate-resilient crops like sweet sorghum. Therefore, this paper aims to review the current efforts at promoting sweet sorghum cultivation in Southern Nigeria and offers a possible approach to hasten it.

Introduction

The recent outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has turned ethanol into a "renewable liquid gold" since it is a primary raw material in the production of sanitizer, in addition to its high demand as biofuel. The expenses of ethanol importation, which were around a quarter of a billion dollars per year in 2007, have risen to a staggering 160 billion Naira (\$414.7 million) in 2020,

despite the fact that local production accounts for only 3% of total ethanol use in Nigeria (Olurounbi, 2020). Nigeria is one of the world's top crude oil exporters, but the country still faces acute energy shortages at home. In cities, the power supply is irregular, and many inhabitants have little or no access to electricity.

The usage of fossil fuels and firewood contributes to a slew of environmental issues that exacerbate climate

change's effects. The negative consequences of Nigeria's reliance on fossil fuels as its primary source of energy and foreign exchange have necessitated the search for alternate energy sources, particularly biofuels. Biofuels have the potential to help solve some of these issues like dwindling economy and environmental degradation. Biofuels are sustainable and cause fewer environmental problems (Reddy *et al.*, 2005). The production of biofuel (ethanol) from food crops such as cassava, sugarcane, and maize, on the other hand, carries the danger of causing a food scarcity. Only ethanol produced from crops that do not jeopardize food security is sustainable in this regard.

Sweet sorghum stands out among biofuel crops. For example, the Nigerian sugarcane industry is still unable to meet domestic sugar demand, and large-scale sugarcane-based ethanol production appears to be a long way off. Ethanol manufacturing from cassava would necessitate the addition of energy and enzymes, and would most likely be prohibitively expensive. In Nigeria, sweet sorghum, which is relatively easy to produce bioethanol, offers certain advantages due to its widespread cultivation. Sweet sorghum, with a combination of easily fermentable sugar and lignocellulose bagasse, has significant potential for high ethanol yield and compares favorably to cassava, sugarcane, and maize in terms of energy balance between production and available extractible sugar. Sweet sorghum ethanol is a sustainable, environmentally friendly energy choice, and sorghum cultivation for ethanol generation will have a direct and long-term influence on gainful youth employment, food security, and enhanced farmer livelihoods.

Climate change has made maintaining national food security considerably more challenging, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. According to 2011 Wet Season Agricultural Performance Survey in Nigeria (NAERLS, NPFS, 2011), sorghum production declined

marginally from 7.02 to 6.89 million tonnes due to a reduction in land area under cultivation from 5.04 million hectares to 4.89 million hectares. This decrease could be owing to the consequences of climate change (severe drought and desert expansion) in the key sorghum-producing area. As a result, there is a need to expand the sorghum-producing frontier down south. Efforts to promote novel crops in a given area frequently fail due to farmer resistance to the crops. This may be due to the farmers' socioeconomic situation, agricultural features (Martinez-Garca *et al.*, 2012), and the lack of economic and sustainable technology to process the products locally. Economic diversification through the promotion of climate-resilient crops like sweet sorghum is one strategy for improving the system and people's resilience to climate change and other stresses. This short review covers the need to promote sweet sorghum farming in Southern Nigeria, as well as potential strategies for doing so. This mini-review discusses the need to promote sweet sorghum cultivation in Southern Nigeria and offers a possible approach to hasten it.

Sweet sorghum

Sweet sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) is a species that includes grain sorghum, grass sorghum, and broom sorghum (Doggett, 1970). It is similar to regularly grown grain sorghum but has a higher potential for sugar accumulation in the stalk. It is a dual-purpose crop, with grain used for food or feed and stalks used to make ethanol. It is the best energy alternative because it doesn't jeopardize food security. Similar to sugarcane, the stalks containing juice are crushed to obtain the juice. Juice content ranges from 12,000 to 20,000 L/ha, depending on genotype, soil, and climatic conditions (Ahmad *et al.*, 2017). Sweet sorghum, like grain sorghum, yields grain (3–7 t/ha), stalk (54–69 t/ha), and Brix range (14.32–22.85%), making it the only crop that can be used to make sugar, ethanol, syrup, feed, bedding, roofing, fencing, and paper (Ahmad *et al.*,

2017). It has a short growing season of about 4-5 months and is drought resistant (Ratnavathi *et al.*, 2011).

Sweet sorghum is a more favorable biomass source, and there is a lot of potential for its sustainable development and use in bioenergy production in Nigeria. From a mix of easily fermentable sugar and lignocellulose bagasse, the crop has significant potential for high ethanol yield, comparing favorably to sugarcane and maize in terms of energy balance between production and available extractable energy. Sweet sorghum ethanol is a sustainable, environmentally friendly energy choice, and sorghum cultivation for ethanol generation will have a direct and long-term influence on gainful young employment, food security, and enhanced farmer livelihoods.

Nigeria produces the most sorghum in West Africa, accounting for over 71% of the region's total sorghum output (Ogbonna, 2011). Sorghum production across the globe totaled 63,930,558 tonnes in 2016, with Nigeria accounting for 10.9 percent of total production (FAOSAT, 2018). After the United States, it is the world's second-largest producer (FAOSTAT, 2018). In 2014, 2015, and 2016, Nigeria produced 6,883,294, 7,005,025 and 6,939,335 tonnes of sorghum, respectively. However, animal feed accounts for 90% of sorghum produced in the United States and India, making Nigeria the world's top producer of food grain sorghum. Sorghum is Nigeria's second most-produced cereal after maize (FAOSTAT, 2018), with over 4.5 million tonnes harvested in 2010, accounting for 25% of total cereal production (FAOSTAT, 2012).

Impacts of climate change on crop production in Nigeria

Climate change is a threat to Nigeria. Nigeria is primarily reliant on rain-fed agriculture, making it vulnerable to the effects of climate change such as heat stress, drought, and flooding (Niang *et al.*, 2014). Climate change is

predicted to have a significant and broad impact on Nigerian agriculture. This is because the effects of climate change frequently result in significant crop yield reductions. According to Ayinde *et al.* (2011), climate change is exerting significant strain on Nigeria's agricultural sector. Climate change is anticipated to affect food crop yields by up to 30% due to poorer productivity and crop failure, according to Jain *et al.* (2015). Food insecurity and human-induced climate change as a result of higher levels of greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere are two intertwined issues that humanity faces in the twenty-first century (Eregha *et al.*, 2014).

Nigeria's varied environment allows it to grow a wide variety of food and cash crops (Tunde *et al.*, 2011). A lot of factors influence crop productivity, including soil, relief, climate, and diseases, among others. Rainfall is one of the most important factors in tropical agriculture since it provides soil moisture for crops. Jidauna *et al.* (2012) investigated the influence of climate change on agricultural activities in a number of Nigerian communities, particularly in the Sudan-Sahel Zone, and reported that rainfall and temperature have reduced and increased, respectively. Crop productivity has decreased and many farmlands are abandoned as a result of this.

Coping with climate change in Nigeria

In order to increase crop output, farmers should employ a variety of adaptation strategies (Eregha *et al.*, 2014). Climate resilience is achieved through implementing strategies for dealing with climate change. Climate resiliency, according to Acevedo *et al.* (2020), is the ability of a socio-ecological system to absorb stress and maintain function in the face of external stresses imposed by climate change, as well as adapt, reorganize, and evolve into more desirable configurations that improve the system's sustainability and prepare it for future climate change impacts. To

meet Africa's climate change challenges, a comprehensive and integrated adaptation system is required (Ozor *et al.*, 2010). The process of responding to or adjusting to the actual and potential repercussions of changing climate conditions in ways that minimize harm and maximize any favorable chances is known as adaptation.

It is currently the most prevalent method of coping with the effects of climate change on agriculture all around the world (Ozor *et al.*, 2012). There are additional policies and programs to reduce exposure to climate unpredictability and extremes, as well as to promote adaptive capability. It necessitates a change in people's perceptions, attitudes, capacities for resilience, and skills. Adaptation and mitigation actions, when carried out simultaneously, can help to lessen the effects of climate change and reduce food security issues (Ozor *et al.*, 2012). Mitigation is required to slow the rate and scale of climate change, while adaptation is required to lessen the effects that cannot be avoided (Ozor and Nnaji, 2010).

Farmers must adapt production and farm management practices to cope with climate change, such as changing planting times, supplementing irrigation (when possible), intercropping, adopting conservation agriculture, gaining access to short- and long-term crop and seed storage infrastructure, and changing crops or planting more climate-resilient crop varieties. Farmers can cope with climate change-induced weather unpredictability by using early-maturing crops, which allow them to adapt planting dates when rains are delayed and reduce the risk of output losses due to drought or heat waves later in the growing season.

Farmers have been compelled to adapt traditional agricultural techniques to current climate-resilient agricultural practices such as crop diversification, planting drought and heat resistant cultivars, soil

maintenance, and rainwater gathering for food security as a result of climate change (Altieri and Nicholls, 2017). Furthermore, market risk, agricultural inputs, enhanced governance, and organizations should all be considered when adopting climate-resilient agriculture techniques (Gentle and Maraseni, 2012; Issaka *et al.*, 2016). Farmers in southern Nigeria have adopted adaptation practices such as changing the timing of land preparation activities, planting dates, harvesting dates, water storage in ponds, groundwater harvesting, mulching/use of cover crops, use of wetlands/river valleys (e.g., Fadama), irrigation schemes, multiple cropping, mixed farming, relay cropping, and intercropping, among others (Ozor *et al.*, 2012).

Crop diversification as a coping strategy

Farmers have historically used crop diversification to tackle crop production problems such as rising input costs, climate change, and increased demand for new products. Crop diversification refers to the cultivation of more than one crop in a given area. Diversification can be achieved by introducing a new crop species or variety, or by altering the current cropping system. Adding more crops to a cropping system is a common example. Diversification can also be used to switch from low-value crops to high-value crops. It is widely acknowledged as one of the most practical, cost-effective, and sensible approaches to creating a resilient agricultural cropping system (Walia, 2020).

Crop diversification allows farmers to spread their production and economic risk among a wider range of crops, lowering the financial risks associated with bad weather or market shocks. Some locations, including a range of crops, can lead to the establishment of new agriculturally based companies, boosting a rural community's economic potential. Furthermore, crop diversification offers humans a more varied and healthier diet. Crop diversification has been recognized as an

effective adaptation option for farmers for risk mitigation, as it has the ability to lower exposure to climate-related risks and increase the flexibility of farm production to changing climatic circumstances (Gebrehiwot and van der Veen, 2013), Crop diversification helps farmers cope with falling crop yields caused by droughts, higher average temperatures, and other climate conditions (Gollin *et al.*, 2005, Lin, 2011). This can be accomplished by growing climate-resilient crops.

Sweet sorghum as a climate-resilient crop

Farmers adopting climate-resilient crops is one of the most important and proactive measures that can be taken to deal with food insecurity caused by unpredictable weather patterns for all countries, but especially for those that rely on rainfed agriculture for food security. Climate-resilient crops and crop types have a higher tolerance for biotic and abiotic stressors (Dhankher and Foyer, 2018). Climate-resilient crops, such as early-maturing cereal, heat-tolerant varieties, drought-tolerant legumes or tuber crops, crops or varieties with enhanced drought and salinity tolerance, or rice with submergence tolerance, can help farmers cope better with climatic change. Climate-resilient crops and crop varieties boost farmers' resilience to climate change, however, despite their benefits; adoption rates by small-scale producers are not as high as expected in many cropping systems (Gollin *et al.*, 2005; Lin, 2011). Sweet sorghum could be considered a climate-resilient crop due to its adaptability to a wide range of climates from the tropics to cool temperate zones, exhibiting short growing cycles, strong tolerance to drought, waterlogging, salinity, and alkalinity.

Promotion of sweet sorghum in southern Nigeria for climate resilience and economic diversification

Previously, it was thought that sorghum could not flourish in southern Nigeria, but research findings have shown that it can thrive there (Alade *et al.*, 2017;

Eniola *et al.*, 2019) through sorghum varietal evaluations and on-farm trials. There is a need to promote sorghum production and build markets that are appealing to local farmers in southern Nigeria. In countries like the US and Brazil, appealing sweet sorghum markets have been built that benefit both small-scale and commercial growers (Nuessly *et al.*, 2013; Viator *et al.*, 2015). In these countries, sweet sorghum is being promoted as a high-priority energy crop for development in order to diversify the source of feedstock for biofuels production. Sweet sorghum development will help to promote agricultural production and livestock husbandry (Fazaeli *et al.*, 2006), energy sources (Nahvi *et al.*, 1994), sugar refining, and paper manufacturing, among other things.

Prior to industrial processing, the sweet sorghum value chain begins with the production of approved planting materials, followed by primary production and on-farm processing for the creation of semi-processed products. The growth of the sweet sorghum industry can help secure food and income, create jobs, and revitalize the rural sector. It can assist address the issues of increased ethanol demand while also providing a way to save money. The processing industry plays an important role in sweet sorghum growth and in attracting small and large sweet sorghum processing businesses to southern Nigeria. Sweet sorghum processing and product development investments should be based on a systematic study of sweet sorghum potential and constraints at each stage of the commodity development cycle. Stakeholders involved in the growth of the sweet sorghum business, including producers, processors, and consumers, as well as connected national, international, and non-governmental organizations, can do so. Support for research and development is critical for overcoming major issues in the production-processing-marketing chain.

Conclusion

Fact that sweet sorghum can be cultivated with fewer inputs, adapts to stress better than traditional crops, and has huge biomass output potential, sweet sorghum has emerged as a possible alternative feedstock for biofuel production. It can thrive and generate acceptable yields in regions where other cereals and crops cannot. It can withstand dryness and grow on low-fertility soils, but it needs irrigation and fertilizer to thrive. It has a low susceptibility to main pests and diseases that impact major staple crops. It has a higher energy output/fossil energy intake than sugarcane, sugar beet, maize, wheat, and other crops. It is more water-efficient (1/3 of the water needed by sugarcane for the same amount of sugar production). In Nigeria, sweet sorghum has the potential to become a major industrial crop. Crop diversification through the use of climate-resilient crops like sweet sorghum is a strategy that will help mitigate the negative impacts of climate change. The promotion of sweet sorghum in southern Nigeria will improve rural livelihoods by generating cash and creating jobs. Furthermore, the national economy should gain both indirectly and directly from employment creation and foreign exchange savings resulting from ethanol importation.

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